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H63D syndrome (Oslo Syndrome) is clinically the iron sibling of Wilson's disease

Abstract

H63D syndrome, now clinically known as Oslo syndrome (synonymous), is considered a very rare disorder that is difficult to recognize due to its multifaceted nature. Even with homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D and the simultaneous presence of the typical clinical symptoms, few clinicians dare to care for affected patients. This is inexplicable, because Oslo syndrome (H63D syndrome) looked at on the meta-level is nothing more than Wilson disease caused by NTBI iron.

H63D syndrome / Oslo syndrome

Evidence-based medicine (not eminence-based medicine) has shown for many years that homozygous mutations of the HFE gene H63D are by no means negligible. Latest since 1999 (Nielsen et al.) it has been known that this mutation can cause polymorph alterations in the carrier's iron metabolism. Not the HFE gene H63D itself is a polymorphism as few, but all the louder "scientists" with good connections to the

pharmaceutical lobby and their chelation pharmaceuticals fantasized in the early days of these new diagnostic methods two and a half decades ago. It is the clinical picture of a homozygous H63D mutation that is terribly polymorph. This means it makes quite some of its carriers ill but the type of anomaly in the iron metabolism can be very different among the patients. H63D usually causes a mild hereditary hemochromatosis only after a second hit, however, it can also cause numerous other disorders of iron metabolism,

such as hypotransferrinemia, changes in binding capacity, etc. which can lead to clinically relevant and even catastrophic symptoms. In addition, it may lead - among other symptoms - to damages of the heart and the substantia nigra via a causal relationship that remains to be investigated, most likely via a cascade-like dysfunction in iron metabolism. The clinical facts are compelling.^{3,9,7,15,16,19,22,24,30,31}

Any physician who dismisses mutations of the HFE gene H63D as clinically irrelevant risks the health of his patients and doesn't work *lege artis* (=not according to scientific medical practices). Therefore all main researcher working on Oslo Syndrome (synonym for the research term "H63D syndrome") have a moral duty to inform the medical community and the public. Homozygous mutations of the HFE gene H63D have not been taken seriously enough for many decades, despite the fact that a homozygous mutation of gene H63D is a Pandora's box. It has been linked to liver disease, bone and joint disease, diabetes mellitus, heart disease, hormonal disorders, porphyria cutanea tarda (PCT), infertility, stroke, severe neurodegenerative disease, cancer, venous peripheral artery disease, hereditary hemochromatosis (after a second hit), and Oslo Syndrome. In the years since the discovery of HFE and its mutations, researchers have focused their studies primarily on the C282Y mutation because it is particularly common in people with elevated iron levels. About 85% of people with abnormally high iron levels have two copies of C282Y, so this mutation has been studied more intensively.^{4,8,22}

Other mutations, such as S65C or H63D, have not attracted the attention of researchers. The S65C mutation can lead to mild to moderate hepatic (liver) iron overload, especially in combination with other mutations. Increased serum iron indices and iron overload have been observed in C282Y/S65C compound heterozygotes. In scientific evaluation, H63D stands out as a significant modifier of disease onset, disease progression and even response to therapy. H63D is associated with arterial rigidity, pro-oxidation, higher total and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, acute lymphoblastic

leukemia, decreased sperm production, and higher risk of type II diabetes mellitus, and hereditary hemochromatosis after a second hit. Being a carrier of a homozygous HFE gene H63D mutation is also a risk factor for earlier onset and longer duration of kidney disease in type II diabetics. The most striking risk associated with H63D is that for neurodegenerative disease. Connor and colleagues were among the first researchers to examine the role of H63D in brain iron accumulation, oxidative stress, and neurotransmitter performance. Connor reported that the HFE variant H63D contributes to many of the processes associated with various types of dementia. These processes include increased cellular iron, oxidative stress (free radical activity), glutamate dyshomeostasis (abnormal balance), and an increase in tau phosphorylation (abnormal levels of tau proteins can lead to dementias such as Alzheimer's disease).²²

As demonstrated by Jacobs, Papadopoulos Kaufmann, and colleagues (2012, 2015, 2017, 2019, 2020, 2021) using solid patient data, the numerous damages in parenchymal tissues, heart, and brain (substantia nigra and basal ganglia) can be explained by insidious non-transferrin-bound iron (NTBI) intoxication as a consequence of chronic transferrin saturation above >50%. This constellation (Oslo Syndrome) is similar to Wilson's disease, except that NTBI iron, rather than copper, is the culprit here. In addition, the damage caused by Oslo Syndrome is more widespread in the body, affecting not only the liver and brain severely but also the heart, and in men, the testes. Synucleinopathies are a major problem of Oslo Syndrome, but other forms of cognitive decline are also common. Connor states further that HFE H63D cells have been shown to have more oxidative stress, further supporting their role as modifiers of neurodegenerative diseases. He found that patients homozygous for H63D had earlier signs of mild cognitive impairment and earlier onset of dementia disease than patients with normal HFE H63D or H63D heterozygote individuals. Despite these crystal clear facts, which have been known for over 25 years, many clinicians still dismiss homozygous HFE-H63D mutations as irrelevant. Even

some of the highest authorities in the field of iron metabolism seem to be trapped in the knowledge of the early 1990s. As physicians specialized in rare diseases, we regularly see patients with complex syndromes consistent with those mentioned before. Just as regularly homozygous mutations of HFE gene H63D are found as *primum movens* (primary cause) of complex metabolic and toxic syndromes. It is also typical for treating colleagues to ignore this finding, as old textbooks (and new ones copy-pasted from old ones) still state that the HFE gene H63D or its homozygous mutation would be clinically irrelevant. This is false, misleading and potentially fatal misinformation. The knowledge about the high clinical relevance is neither new nor a fringe topic. HFE H63D is not a strong hemochromatosis gene, however, with a second hit it can easily cause hereditary hemochromatosis. Even more crucial than this, a homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D is, according to overwhelming evidence, responsible for many cases of complex syndromes associated with heterogeneously altered iron metabolism. It is evident from all this that Oslo Syndrome is a not so very distant relative of Wilson's disease, only with NTBI iron instead of copper as the causative agent. But why does every GP/primary care provider have at least some basic knowledge of Wilson's disease and not Oslo Syndrome?^{9,12,25,32,33,35} It was concluded, after professional discussion in the centers of competence, that the term H63D syndrome is difficult to remember and, moreover, does not do justice to the multifaceted nature of the disease. Therefore H63D syndrome was renamed Oslo Syndrome (for clinical settings) as a result of the International H63D Syndrome Conference in 2022. Why Oslo? In the Norwegian capital, researchers from around the world agreed for the first time on the leading symptoms of H63D syndrome. Only seemingly independent diseases. It's a one cause syndrome. As we shall discuss later, narcolepsy with cataplexy is a hallmark symptom of brain damage in Oslo Syndrome. However, there is an anomaly in Oslo Syndrome patients. As Adams et al. (2021) could prove Oslo Syndrome patients who "succeeded" in inhibiting an incipient seizure and did not fall asleep developed other

symptoms that appear to the observer as "sleep-related partial inhibition or reduction of body functions while being awake". This is a broad area for future research, as it may even help explain comorbidities in primary narcolepsy. There are more symptoms to be found in this very unique phenomenon after attack inhibition. In order to not overwhelm the reader we focussed here on the most important ones: interestingly, the reduced function of gastric motility in particular could be part of the explanation why narcoleptics tend to be overweight. On the one hand, during inhibited attacks there is still food in their stomach from meals taken hours ago and, at the same time, other biosensors send signals to the brain that it is time to eat again. Thus, even during and shortly after a narcoleptic seizure, we see slightly elevated serum glucose levels, even if full seizures have been inhibited and the patient has remained awake. These values suddenly drop again once gastric motility returns to normal.

IQ decline in H63D/Oslo syndrome

A significant number of patients with H63D syndrome develops dementia, most likely due to synucleinopathy. Independent of this issue, a significant drop in IQ can be observed in more than 72% of patients compared to corresponding control groups (Fig. 3). Also executive functions might deteriorate to a remarkable extent. To date, we do not have a satisfactory explanation for this aspect, which is probably still substantially underestimated because the effects are less noticeable in everyday life when compared to dementia. Nevertheless, a linear 50% decrease in professionally measured IQ, as shown in the table below, is not only highly significant but also concerning. Considering that most patients have a job with certain responsibilities, a significant decline in IQ is a matter of public safety. In this case, physicians must not look away simply because IQ loss is a difficult matter to communicate. As the signs are more subtle than those of dementia, families and caregivers must also learn to recognize the signs and symptoms of IQ loss. One very common early sign is a rise in accidental writing errors, may they be misspelling or

using associated words like “wood” instead of “tree”. In most cases, the diagnosis is still made too late, which leads to dangerous work errors, failures in the household, problems keeping up intellectually with peers and the danger of overestimating one's own abilities. Since science and medicine have yet to answer the question of which of the brain damages due to NTBI causes this brain symptom in Oslo Syndrome, let alone how to treat this IQ loss, counseling is usually helpful in learning to live with this progressive limitation. Interestingly, the issue of memory impairment does not seem to match in any way with this loss of brain power we see in patients with Oslo Syndrome. Our patients can remember but not use their knowledge as they could in the past. It's like they know exactly what a puzzle is and how it should work, but they are not able anymore to use this knowledge in a practical way. So, a businessman with an IQ of 65 at age 47 is not as mentally capable as he was with an IQ of 119 when he graduated from college, even without losing his memory. Because he has no memory loss and since he can still remember things quite well, most people around him will not notice his sharp cognitive decline and distorted executive functions until he makes a big mistake. Therefore, depending on the profession, it should not be a taboo to make these patients leave their jobs (retire) even against their will if their IQ has dropped by 25% within 10 years or if their IQ falls below a cut-off range of 75-85, depending on their job.⁴³

Heart conditions due to Oslo Syndrome

Cardiac problems are very common in Oslo Syndrome, however, they can be of diverse etiology. Chronically elevated eosinophils, palpitation, calcium channel dysfunction, fibrosis, conduction disturbances (heart blocks) - all of these can occur at high NTBI levels and cause transient and permanent damage. Despite transient symptoms may occur, severity and permanence correlates positively with age. With Oslo Syndrome being an NTBI driven iron poisoning, this correlation makes sense as well as the fact that younger Oslo Syndrome patients often report VES/SVES. Low NTBI accumulations seems to cause “harmless” functional issues

while a more NTBI can lead to severe damage, as far as heart-failure.

Testicular damage in Oslo Syndrome patients

Since NTBI has a strong affinity for parenchymal tissue, the male gonads are a preferred target for this form of free iron. There, it penetrates the cells, causing oxidative damage and, as a consequence, non-dramatic but significant regressive damage to the testes. On sonography (including Doppler), the tissue appears homogeneous, but scarce microlithiasis can be seen bilaterally with more modern sonography equipment, usually models built after 2010. Older sonography devices may miss microlithiasis because the calcifications are often too small for their resolving power. Patients with microlithiasis should be followed up closely for quite a period of time, especially if under 45 years of age, as microlithiasis can occasionally be a sign of testicular cancer or an early warning sign of this undesirable condition. Usually the damage is bilateral, we have not had a case where only one testicle was affected. The spermiogram usually shows somewhat decreased fertility, but this has not become uncommon in the general male population anyway. So far, we are not aware of any treatment that could stop the regressive process in Oslo Syndrome. However, since the effect is usually rather mild, few patients (or their partners) are likely to consider this a relevant problem. Therefore, this aspect of Oslo Syndrome is still largely unknown to urologists and andrologists.³²⁻³⁶

Fat metabolism

Patients with advanced Oslo Syndrome often have elevated triglyceride levels with quite high postprandial peaks. In how far this contributes to the development to Steatosis hepatis is still unclear. However, there is a logical connection between both phenomena. A causality still has to be proven.³⁶

H63D/Oslo Syndrome in TCS Sonography

In transcranial sonography (TCS), and only in TCS, degeneration of the substantia nigra (brain) is detected in 80-90% of patients with H63D/Oslo syndrome around the age of 40, largely identical to the findings known from Parkinson's disease. The bright foci are iron-rich degenerated brain structures, and in H63D/Oslo syndrome some of the iron has been "carried in". The other part comes from the destroyed brain structures. Note: NTBI iron and these fine-grained lesions are not seen on MRI, CT, or liver biopsy.

Substantia nigra echogenicity (normal) in a healthy individual

Substantia nigra hyper-echogenicity as found in H63D syndrome

Transcranial ultrasound (TCS) is of paramount importance in patients suffering from advanced stages of Oslo-Syndrome. Caused by a homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D, H63D/Oslo Syndrome is known for its diverse symptomatology. However, you will hardly find an Oslo Syndrome patient without tics, REM sleep disorders and/or narcolepsy with cataplexy, distorted executive functions, cardiac damage, liver dysfunction and, not infrequently, damage to the male gonads. Transcranial sonography often shows a Parkinson's-like pattern from the 5th decade of life. As was presented in previous studies³¹⁻³⁴ narcolepsy with cataplexy is a cardinal symptom of advanced Oslo Syndrome that correlates with findings consistent with brain damage on transcranial sonography (hyper-echogenicity in the substantia nigra and abnormal findings in parts of the basal ganglia), as shown in Fig. 1 at the end of this chapter. TCS is the only method with which one can make NTBI visible. MRI, CT, PET and even biopsies will provide a false-negative result. In biopsies it is due to the fact that NTBI cannot be stained with Prussian blue, a fact that even some histopathologists are not aware of. In another study (Seideman et al. 2021) 200 patients with relevant cataplexy seizures, defined as more than 2 seizures with falls and/or injuries

and/or property damage, aged 24 to 49 years, mean age 32 (169 male, 31 female, no significant sex difference in results) were interviewed using structured questionnaires about their symptoms, course of disease, other aspects of their condition; and each of them had at least one transcranial sonography with modern equipment and physicians very highly trained for this very specific type of ultrasound procedure. The researchers asked the sonography experts to provide, in addition to their normal reports, a severity scale ranging from zero (normal substantia nigra) to ten (very hyper-echogenic substantia nigra). They found a striking patterns consistent with the anecdotal description of disease progression as reported by the patients themselves (Fig. 2). As can be seen well in this pooled graph, there seems to be a strong inverse correlation between certain motor symptoms (e.g., tics, hyperkinesia) and narcolepsy with cataplexy. The differences between male and female patients are not significant. The results of transcranial sonography are even more striking. Damage to the substantia nigra appears to correlate with a sharp increase in symptom severity of narcolepsy plus cataplexy in Oslo Syndrome patients, with tics decreasing the more substantia nigra damage becomes visible in TCS. To date, no satisfactory explanation exists for this finding. The fact that the Oslo Syndrome does not fit into any pre-existing box has been obvious since the beginning of research on the subject. However, the finding that narcolepsy (with cataplexy) is a marker for brain damage progression has important consequences for diagnosis and treatment. For some time, there were discussions and attempts to control the motor symptoms of Oslo Syndrome patients with levodopa. One of the side effects of levodopa is actually narcolepsy. However, the levodopa treatment path has been abandoned which is good news for the patients. Thus, levodopa cannot explain the inverse correlation of symptom development. The strikingly similar course of damage to the substantia nigra and parts of the basal ganglia seen on transcranial sonography is a strong indication that the destruction and scarring in this brain region must underlie the answer to this highly interesting and significant phenomenon. At the same time, it should caution clinicians to

be careful about administering levodopa to patients with Oslo Syndrome. To an outside observer, tics and symptoms of hyperkinesia may appear drastic, but the heavier burden on the patients is severe narcolepsy with cataplexy. Frontline clinicians should be aware of this symptom shift from often very severe tics in H63D syndrome to narcolepsy with cataplexy while all other symptoms of this serious illness remain progressive:¹⁻³⁶

- Static or semi-static hypotransferrinemia (non-/semi-reactive after iron ingestion)
- Chronically elevated transferrin saturation >50-55% (multiple testing is recommended due to nutrient-related fluctuations)
- Deposition of NTBI iron in brain and parenchymal tissue
- Progressive degeneration of substantia nigra and parts of basal ganglia
- Thought disorders (often severe and usually primarily obsessive in nature, compatible with dysfunction of the basal ganglia).
- Tic disorders (variable, often Tourette-like, partly including danger of self-injury)
- REM sleep disorders with risk of self-injury
- Variable motor disorders (in the late course possibly also Parkinson's symptoms)
- Synucleinopathies of various degrees of severity (from mild cognitive impairment to dementia)
- Executive function impairment
- Drop in IQ measurement results
- Postural instability (equal to Parkinson's disease)
- Non-motor Parkinson's symptoms
- Loss of the olfactory sense
- Chronic constipation
- Narcolepsy, often with cataplexy, often severe. If degenerative brain damage has already manifested the progression of narcolepsy can be used as a marker for brain damage with the same diagnostic value as a positive transcranial sonography
- Disturbances in coordination and fine motor skills
- Psychological abnormalities such as depression or personality changes

- Cardiac damage and cardiac dysfunction (especially conduction defects and arrhythmias)
- Heart failure
- Liver damage (even in the early course often an unexplainable fatty degeneration of the liver aka non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD))
- Diabetes type 2
- Excessive reactions of the non-adaptive immune system with unpredictable autoimmune reactions
- Disturbed movements in the digestive system (partial paralysis, similar to the issues that are known from Parkinson's syndrome)
- Low to moderate shrinkage of testicular tissue in male patients with degenerative signs on sonography incl. microlithiasis
- Variable skin symptoms (especially itching blisters)
- Mild eosinophilia and/or basophilia
- Hyper-reaction of the innate immune system
- Petechia (without any pathological signal in any lab test)
- Rare: Renal involvement, ocular disease due to NTBI induced oxidative processes, hearing loss, etc.

Treatment and Prognosis

Unlike hemochromatosis Oslo Syndrome is not well treatable. This is because other than ferritin, NTBI iron cannot be easily removed from the body. In emergencies, plasma infusions or chelation therapies can remove an acute overload of NTBI iron from the organism. However, all these methods are risky, only helpful for a short time and thus neither reasonable nor sustainable in the chronically ill. At best, one can try to reduce the transferrin saturation (TFsat) to below 50%, or better below 45%, by means of a low-iron diet. However, since many patients with H63D/Oslo syndrome have low to very low ferritin levels, such a diet should only be undertaken under close medical supervision. The prognosis is poor. Especially if organ damage has already manifested. However, we treat in a symptom-relieving manner and improve quality of life quite effectively with a Oslo Syndrome specific medication and diet plan.

Wilson's disease

Morbus Wilson, known as Wilson's disease, is a hereditary copper storage syndrome, as is Oslo syndrome with respect to NTBI iron. Due to a genetic defect, copper excretion is impaired, causing copper to accumulate in and damage the liver, central nervous system, and other organs. The organism does not excrete enough copper and it accumulates in the body. Affected individuals suffer primarily from liver damage and neurological complaints, but also from cardiac, ophthalmologic and many other symptoms. Liver conditions such as liver enlargement, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), hepatitis, jaundice and abdominal pain, cardiac and neurological symptoms such as muscle stiffness, tremor, speech disorders and personality changes occur progressively. The Prognosis is good with early diagnosis and consistent therapy, and life expectancy is not limited. However, untreated Wilson disease is fatal. Physical examination, blood and urine tests, eye examination, possibly a liver biopsy are part of the diagnostic process. Drugs that promote copper excretion or inhibit copper absorption in the intestine, can help, in very progressed liver disease a transplantation might be considered.

Further insights

The name Wilson's disease goes back to the physician Samuel Wilson, who first described the symptoms and their causes. In this hereditary disease, there is a change (mutation) in a gene (carrier of the genetic material) that triggers the disease. The gene contains the blueprint for the so-called Wilson protein, a copper transport protein. Wilson's disease only occurs when the mutation is present in both parents and both pass it on to the child. About one person in 30,000 is diagnosed with Wilson's disease. However, clinicians rightfully estimate that the disease is not diagnosed in many affected people, so there is a high number of unreported cases. The first mild symptoms of Wilson's disease usually appear in childhood, with liver anomalies being the first symptom of the disease. Symptoms of the nervous system usually do not appear until

after the age of ten. Children with any type of liver anomaly (even mild ones) are suspicious to suffer from a genetic disorder like Wilson's disease, H63D/Oslo syndrome, hereditary hemochromatosis, and others. Studies show that during the course of the disease, liver damage occurs in all affected individuals with copper storage disease. This ranges from an asymptomatic increase in liver values to fatty liver (NAFLD) and liver inflammation (NASH/hepatitis). If the liver damage progresses further, cirrhosis of the liver occurs, in which the liver tissue increasingly transforms into functionless connective tissue.³⁷⁻⁴²

The most common symptoms in late stage Wilson's disease

- Jaundice (icterus) with yellowing of the skin and mucous membranes
- Enlargement of the liver
- Abdominal pain
- Liver failure
- Severe damage to the nervous system
- Involuntary tremor
- Stiffness of the muscles
- Slowed movements
- Speech and writing disorders
- Disturbances in coordination and fine motor skills
- Psychological abnormalities such as depression or personality changes
- Copper deposits in the cornea of the eye (Kayser-Fleischer corneal ring)
- skin changes
- excessive pigmentation
- spider nevi
- anemia due to hemolysis
- kidney damage
- cardiac damages or arrhythmias
- muscle weakness

Treatment of Wilson's disease

Wilson's disease is based on a change in the genetic information and therefore cannot be cured with medication, but it can be treated well. If the pediatrician diagnoses the disease early in childhood, the prognosis is good and life expectancy is not reduced. However, if the clinicians fail to catch the illness early all symptoms mentioned before can occur. Missing Wilson's disease should

not happen but it still does happen on a daily basis. So, if the liver is already very severely damaged, liver failure may occur. In this case, liver transplantation will be discussed. The disease can be cured by transplantation because the cells of the donor liver contain an intact Wilson gene, which normalizes copper metabolism. Without proper treatment, Wilson's disease is fatal within a couple of years. Patients die both from severe liver damage and from severe neurological impairment.^{37,38}

Risk factors and detection

The cause of Wilson's disease is a genetic change (mutation). However, this only causes Wilson's disease if both parents have the mutation and pass it on to their child. The mutation is passed on from generation to generation. Children of healthy parents who both carry the defective gene have a 25 percent chance of being affected. More than 350 different mutations are known for the mutated Wilson gene. It is responsible for the formation of a protein that transports copper. If the function of this protein is impaired by the mutation, the body no longer excretes sufficient copper via the bile and stores it increasingly in the liver. This is only possible to a limited extent, the liver becomes inflamed and the copper is washed into the blood. In this way, it also reaches the brain and other organs and accumulates there. If copper storage disease is suspected, the physician palpates the abdomen and performs a (contrast enhanced) sonography of the abdomen and the liver to detect any concerning changes. The neurological status and performance will be tested by an experienced neurologist. Laboratory tests will include (in addition to liver function parameters) a test to detect ceruloplasmin which is involved in copper metabolism, is of particular importance. Its concentration is often reduced in people with Wilson's disease. An increased copper concentration can also be detected in the patient's urine. The concentration of copper in the blood, on the other hand, plays a subordinate role in the diagnosis, a pitfall for unexperienced physicians. In addition, the copper content of the liver is significantly increased in Wilson's disease. This can be detected by a

liver biopsy. However, a liver biopsy is usually only necessary in Wilson's disease if the other tests do not yield a clear result like the ophthalmologic slit lamp test to detect the typical Kayser-Fleischer corneal ring around the iris. An MRI scan (not CT or PET) of the head can rule out the possibility that neurological symptoms - such as movement disorders - are due to other brain diseases. Important to remember: despite the extreme havoc copper can cause in the central nervous system MRI results may not reflect the clinical reality - yet another potential pitfall. We see the same in H63D/Oslo syndrome in which MRI, CT and PET remain 'silent' while transcranial sonography is able to reflect the devastations in Substantia nigra.³⁹⁻⁴²

Chelation, Zinc and diets

The change in the genetic material that underlies Wilson's disease cannot be directly corrected. Therefore, drugs are used to keep the levels of copper in the body stable. Chelating agents are drugs that bind the copper present in the body. This enables the body to excrete the copper more easily. Even a simple substance like zinc can be helpful. In the intestine, zinc ensures that the body absorbs less copper from food. It is mainly used in patients who do not yet show symptoms and during pregnancy. Quite often there is a worsening of neurological symptoms during therapy with chelation agents. In this case, too, the treating physicians sometimes opt for zinc. Again one of dozens of similarities to H63D/Oslo syndrome in which chelation can aggravate the symptoms due to the insidious nature of NTBI iron. If the diagnosis is made too late or treatment is unsuccessful in Wilson's disease and progressive liver failure has already manifested, liver transplantation might be required. Thus, as with H63D/Oslo syndrome, early diagnosis is critical. For patients suffering from Wilson's disease, it is advisable to pay attention to a low copper diet. The same applies to patients with H63D/Oslo syndrome, but in relation to a low-iron diet. Although a diet alone is not sufficient, it supports the drug treatment. Above all, it is advisable to eliminate foods with a high copper content from the diet,

such as crustaceans, offal, raisins, nuts or cocoa. In addition, those affected should have the copper content of their tap water tested. In some households, water pipes contain copper, which passes into the tap water.³⁷⁻⁴²

Discussion

There are two levels to classify a syndrome. First biological, second clinical. On the biological level, there are structural similarities of pathogenesis between H63D/Oslo syndrome and Wilson's disease. However, the clinical level is more pivotal. Here, both diseases are largely similar. This has implications for clinical practice and treatment. As long as H63D syndrome is falsely classified as a strange type of hemochromatosis, it remains a difficult-to-understand outsider phenomenon. If, however, it is associated with the 80% overlapping clinical analogue Wilson's disease, the syndrome can be understood adequately. In this case physicians and patients will have the chance to understand what they are really dealing with. This is of significant importance for diagnosis, treatment and early detection.

Conclusion

We demonstrated that it may be fatal to locate H63D syndrome aka Oslo syndrome as an exotic disorder in the field of hemochromatosis. H63D/Oslo syndrome is not as rare as once thought. It is just too rarely diagnosed. It should be considered independently of all other disorders of iron metabolism. This is especially true for both hemochromatosis and neurodegeneration with brain iron accumulation (NBIA). H63D/Oslo syndrome is not correctly classified clinically unless it is considered the NTBI iron form of Wilson disease. This analogy is not scientifically correct, but it is clinically more accurate than any other classification. This fact should raise clinicians' awareness and not leave them clueless when faced with patients who suffer from H63D syndrome aka Oslo syndrome.

Conflicts of interest

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